
D6.5 / Midterm report on project visibility and educational material

Editor	Contractual delivery	Actual delivery
Kristina Leipuviene (SSOL)	February 2026	February 2026
Deliverable type	Dissemination level	Version - date
R - Document, report	PU – Public	1.0 - 23/02/2026

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Deliverable ID

Project acronym	AI-PROGNOSIS
Project full title	Artificial intelligence-based Parkinson's disease risk assessment and prognosis
Grant Agreement ID	101080581
Deliverable number	D6.5
Deliverable title	Midterm report on project visibility and educational material
Work package	WP6 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation
Deliverable type	R - Document, report
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Version - date	1.0 – 23/02/2026
Contractual delivery	February 2026
Actual delivery	February 2026
Lead partner	SSOL
Editor	Kristina Leipuviene (SSOL)
Contributors	Therese Scott-Duncan (UU); John Zaras (SQD); Ioannis Drivas (DBC); Stelios Hadjidimitriou (AUTH)
Reviewed by	John Zaras (SQD) David Lyreskog (UOXF)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
Keywords	Communication, clustering, dissemination, educational material, networking, visibility

Document history

Version	Date	Contributors	Action / status
0.1	02/12/2025	SSOL	Document structure (table of contents) ready
0.2	15/12/2025	SSOL	Document structure (table of contents) revised
0.3	20/01/2026	UU	Section 4 Educational material
0.4	28/01/2026	SSOL	Section 4 revised
0.5	29/01/2026	SSOL	Ready for internal review
0.5	13/02/2026	SQD, UOXF	Document reviewed by John Zaras (SQD) and David Lyreskog (UOXF)
0.6	19/02/2026	SSOL	Document revised
0.7	23/02/2026	AUTH	Minor revisions-additions; Approved by the Coordinator for submission
1.0	23/02/2026	AUTH	Submitted version

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DHU	Digital Health Uptake
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HCPs	Healthcare Professionals
HRB	Horizon Results Booster
IT	Information Technology
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MSc	Master of Science
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PwP	People with Parkinson's Disease
R&I	Research and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Deliverable D6.5, “Midterm report on project visibility and educational material” summarises dissemination, communication, clustering, networking, and educational content development activities carried out within the AI-PROGNOSIS project through the period M19–M32. The report builds on the foundations established during the first reporting period (M1–M18) and reflects the project’s continued implementation of its dissemination and communication strategy across scientific, clinical, industry, and non-academic contexts.

Communication and dissemination activities continued across multiple channels, including the project website, newsletters, social media, and participation in scientific and business events. During the M19–M32 reporting period, six scientific publications were produced, including two peer-reviewed journal publications, with one additional peer-reviewed journal article accepted and awaiting publication. One article was also published in a business-oriented outlet. The project was presented at five scientific conferences, four business and industry events, and 13 workshops, seminars, and special sessions, reaching academic, clinical, industry, and patient audiences.

Stakeholder engagement activities during M19–M32 also included hands-on demo sessions and co-creation activities with end-users. Four demo sessions were conducted using early pre-Minimum Viable Product (MVP) versions of the project tools, including sessions with members of the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel for the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications and one demo session with clinicians for mAI-Insights. In parallel, 11 co-creation workshops involving people with Parkinson’s disease (PwP) and healthcare professionals (HCPs) were carried out to support user research, application design, and iterative refinement of the digital tools.

Online communication activities continued throughout the period. Regular website updates, social media posting, and newsletter dissemination supported ongoing outreach. Newsletter subscriptions and social media followers increased compared to the previous reporting period, while website traffic remained stable but below the target defined in the project KPIs.

Clustering and networking activities were expanded during M19–M32 through collaboration with sister projects and other EU-funded initiatives. Key activities included the co-organisation of a workshop and participation in a panel session at IEEE HealthCom 2025, as well as contribution to a joint session at the Health Data Summit 2025 alongside other Horizon Europe projects. The project also took part in plenary meetings and thematic exchanges with the iPROLEPSIS project and remained active in the Stay Healthy Cluster Communication and Dissemination Task Force with sister projects. In parallel, the formal cluster with Horizon Europe projects iPROLEPSIS and REBECCA was established with support of Booster services. Additional networking by partners took place through participation in international neurology and healthcare conferences.

Educational content development activities continued during the reporting period. Educational materials were co-created and reviewed by PwP and HCPs to ensure relevance, clarity, and high quality. During M19–M32, new educational articles, dictionary entries, and quizzes were produced. In addition, a non-academic outreach webinar with PwP supported the identification of topics of interest for further educational materials, including planned infographics. Further enrichment of educational content will continue in the next phase of the project.

This deliverable contributes to Work Package 6 (WP6) and supports the objectives set out in earlier deliverables, including D6.2 and D6.3. It is associated with the implementation of Tasks T6.1 – Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring, T6.2 –

Clustering and networking activities, and T6.3 – PD educational content development. It is also connected to Work Package 2 (WP2), in particular Task T2.2 – User research and co-creation, through the reporting of co-creation workshops and hands-on feedback sessions with end-users, and to Work Package 4 (WP4), specifically Task T4.2 – Application design and development, which focuses on user-centred design, application development, and iterative testing.

The next and final reporting on project visibility and educational material will be presented in Deliverable D6.6, “Final report on project visibility and educational material”, scheduled for M48.

1 Introduction

D6.5, “Midterm report on project visibility and educational material” presents a detailed overview of dissemination, communication, clustering, and educational content development carried out by the consortium during the M19–M32 period.

Building on the first reporting phase (M1–M18), the project has continued to strengthen its efforts to engage target audiences, raise awareness about Parkinson’s disease (PD), and increase visibility through strategic communication channels. This report highlights the implementation of the dissemination and communication plan, the creation of PD-related educational content, and the clustering and networking efforts. Progress is assessed using the project’s Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

This deliverable is part of WP6, “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”, and builds on earlier deliverables, particularly D6.2, “Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan”¹ and D6.3, “First report on project visibility and educational material”².

1.1 Document scope

Deliverable D6.5 covers the period from M19 to M32 and serves as the midterm report on project visibility and educational material under WP6. It focuses on the implementation, evolution, and impact of dissemination and communication activities, networking and clustering efforts, and the development of educational content related to PD and AI-based digital health solutions.

Specifically, this deliverable reports on activities linked to the following WP6 tasks:

- T6.1 – Dissemination and communication planning, implementation and monitoring
- T6.2 – Clustering and networking activities
- T6.3 – PD educational content development.

It is also linked with the work carried out in WP4, specifically T4.2 – Application design and development, which includes regular development sprints and stakeholder feedback sessions following major releases in close collaboration with T2.2 – User research and co-creation.

The document includes:

- Summary of outreach activities through the website, social media, newsletters, and participation in conferences, workshops, and other events
- Overview of scientific and business publications
- Progress on the development of educational content focused on PD
- Engagement in joint activities with related EU-funded initiatives and other stakeholders’ involvement initiatives, and
- Evaluation of progress against KPIs defined in the Description of Action (DoA).

This deliverable complements D6.3 and feeds into the final reporting that will be delivered through D6.6, “Final report on project visibility and educational material” scheduled for the end of the project (M48).

¹ D6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, <https://zenodo.org/records/15542728>

² D6.3 First report on project visibility and educational material, <https://zenodo.org/records/15542770>

1.2 Document structure

This document provides an overview of dissemination, communication, networking activities, and educational material developed within the AI-PROGNOSIS project during M19–M32. It is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the purpose, scope, and structure of the report
- **Section 2** outlines the overall dissemination and communication strategy, including target audiences, project identity, and communication tools
- **Section 3** presents project visibility activities across media channels, including the website, social media, newsletters, publications, events, and partner contributions
- **Section 4** covers the planning and development of PD educational content, including articles, videos, quizzes, and other materials
- **Section 5** details clustering and networking activities, including partnerships, collaboration with sister projects, Booster services and partners networking efforts
- **Section 6** evaluates progress against the dissemination and communication KPIs, and
- **Section 7** summarises the main outcomes of the midterm period and outlines perspectives for the remaining project duration.

2 Dissemination and communication approach

Deliverable D6.2, “Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan”, details the dissemination and communication strategy, objectives and approach and serves as a background for planning and implementing the activities described in this deliverable.

2.1 Overall strategy

The AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication strategy is designed to be dynamic and adaptable, allowing it to evolve in line with project progress, emerging results, and feedback from stakeholders. While the core strategy was established in D6.2, its implementation continued to mature during the midterm phase as more concrete outputs became available.

During this reporting period, the focus gradually shifted from initial awareness-raising to more active dissemination and engagement, including increased participation in scientific and business and industry events, regular online communication, and the gradual development of PD-related educational content. At the same time, networking and clustering activities with related EU-funded initiatives were strengthened to support knowledge exchange and joint visibility.

The overall objectives of the dissemination and communication activities remain aligned with those defined in D6.2 and include:

- Disseminating scientific achievements of the project and making the outputs widely available for research and business purposes in the long-term
- Informing key stakeholders about project objectives, progress, results and their innovation potential
- Increasing awareness and engagement of people with and at risk of PD for addressing their issues and concerns to increase their awareness and build trust in new technology
- Reaching similar and relevant R&I projects for promoting networking and joint activities, and

- Establishing a forum/community for Health Care Professionals (HCPs) and authorities to develop new guidelines and standards.

To achieve these objectives, a multi-channel approach continues to be applied, combining scientific publications and conferences with digital communication tools such as the project website, social media, newsletters, and educational materials. Messages are tailored to different stakeholder groups while maintaining consistent project branding and core messaging.

Progress and impact are monitored through the KPIs defined in the Description of Action (DoA) and D6.2, allowing activities to be adjusted where needed and ensuring that dissemination and communication efforts remain measurable and traceable.

2.2 Target audience

The target audiences for AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication activities remain consistent with those identified in D6.2. These include:

- Persons with PD (PwP), their families, carers, and PD advocacy and research associations
- The relevant primary and secondary HCPs³
- The relevant scientific and technical community, i.e., clinical, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and ethics research scientists and designers/developers of human-centred health technologies
- The relevant industry leaders, e.g., mobile health (mHealth), medical AI, and pharmaceutical industry, and
- The healthcare enablers and policymakers.

Different dissemination and communication objectives are pursued for each audience, ranging from sharing scientific findings and collecting expert feedback, to raising awareness, fostering trust, and encouraging engagement with project activities and results.

A combination of channels is used to reach these groups, including scientific publications and conferences, workshops and stakeholder events, demo sessions, newsletters, social media, and the project website. This diversified approach ensures that AI-PROGNOSIS objectives, progress, and results are communicated effectively to a broad and diverse audience, while remaining accessible and relevant to each stakeholder group.

2.3 Project identity

The visual identity and branding of AI-PROGNOSIS were established at the beginning of the project and remain unchanged during the current reporting period (M19–M32). The project's logo, colour palette, animated logo video, and communication templates were developed to ensure a unified and recognisable identity across all dissemination and communication materials and channels.

These branding elements are described in detail D6.1, "Project branding and communication channels"⁴, which outlines the development of the visual materials and social media guidelines. D6.3 also presents the visual identity components introduced earlier in the project. As no updates were made during this reporting period, the original branding remains fully applicable.

³ https://www.physio-pedia.com/Levels_of_Healthcare

⁴ D6.1 Project branding and communication channels, <https://zenodo.org/records/15542693>

All visual identity assets continue to be used consistently and remain accessible to the consortium partners via the internal repository and the project website, in the “Knowledge base” section under “Communication Kit”⁵.

2.4 Communication kit

The AI-PROGNOSIS communication kit⁶, including a poster, flyer and roll-up banner, ensures consistent, professional and recognisable communication across dissemination and communication activities. These materials continue to support project visibility and outreach at conferences, public events, and stakeholder engagement activities (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1 AI-PROGNOSIS promotional materials used at events

During the reporting period, the communication kit was expanded with the addition of a project overview presentation⁷, supporting structured and coherent project communication. In addition, QR codes linking to the project presentation were added to project poster, flyer, and roll-up banner to facilitate easy access to project information (**Figure 2**).

⁵ AI-PROGNOSIS promo materials <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/communication-kit>

⁶ AI-PROGNOSIS Communication kit, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/communication-kit>

⁷ AI-PROGNOSIS [project presentation](#)

Figure 2 AI-PROGNOSIS Poster (on the left) and Roll-up banner (on the right)

3 Project visibility

3.1 Media

AI-PROGNOSIS utilises various media-based communication to increase project visibility, disseminate results, raise awareness, attract interest and offer information to various stakeholders. This communication is based on four different activities, namely:

- Website posts
- Social media posts
- Newsletters, and
- Major media (TV/radio).

Communication efforts through the project website and social media channels have been ongoing since the beginning of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, ensuring continuous engagement and dissemination of project-related information.

3.1.1 Website

3.1.1.1 Updates

The AI-PROGNOSIS website⁸ remains the main platform for sharing project updates, results, and dissemination materials with external stakeholders. Since the previous reporting period,

⁸ AI-PROGNOSIS website, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/>

the website has been expanded with several new sections, including **Survey**⁹, **Patient voices**¹⁰ and **Deliverables**¹¹ (Figure 3):

- The **Survey** section hosts an online questionnaire on the AI-PROGNOSIS toolkit for Parkinson’s disease care, collecting input from people with Parkinson’s disease, relatives, and healthcare professionals
- The **Patient Voices** section features insights from members of the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel, sharing personal experiences of living with Parkinson’s disease as well as their motivation and pathway for becoming involved in the AI-PROGNOSIS project
- The **Deliverables** section provides open access to public project deliverables from the first reporting period, which are made available via Zenodo, supporting transparency and dissemination to external stakeholders.

Figure 3 Updated website with new sections – Survey, Deliverables, and Patient Voices

In addition, the Learning Hub has been further enriched with new educational content, including six articles, three interactive quizzes, and several dictionary entries, supporting the project’s efforts to improve awareness and understanding of PD and related digital health topics (Figure 4).

⁹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/survey>

¹⁰ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/patient-voices>

¹¹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/deliverables>

Figure 4 New educational content on the Learning hub

The website is frequently updated, with an average of four posts per month, covering news, event participation, publications and project developments. It also includes downloadable materials and newsletters (Figure 5). Website engagement was further supported through the use of QR codes in social media posts and dissemination materials, linking directly to the online survey and relevant website sections.

Figure 5 Newsroom section on the AI-PROGNOSIS website

During M19–M32, the website received an average of 335 visits per month, which remained below the planned KPI of 1,000 visitors per month (Figure 6). However, this represents a

clear increase compared to the M1–M18 period, during which the website received an average of 183 visits per month, as reported in D6.3.

Figure 6 Monthly website page views 2025 01 – 2026 01

One factor contributing to the lower recorded traffic is that, in line with GDPR requirements, Wix traffic reports include analytics data only from visitors who have accepted the cookie consent policy. As a result, website traffic statistics may not fully capture all visits, which can affect the completeness of recorded visibility metrics.

The website will continue to serve as a key channel for publishing project outcomes and engaging stakeholders as AI-PROGNOSIS progresses toward its final phase.

3.1.1.2 GDPR compliance

The AI-PROGNOSIS website follows a GDPR-compliant approach to personal data protection, transparency and user rights. The website’s Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy¹² were updated in March 2025 and are publicly available, clearly describing what personal data are collected, how they are processed, and for which purposes.

Personal data are processed only on a lawful basis, primarily by user consent or legal obligations. The website uses a cookie consent mechanism that allows visitors to accept or decline non-essential cookies. We have also adopted the requirements foreseen in the GDPR and the ePrivacy Directive to ensure the use of a compliant “cookie banner”, which offer the users the option to manage them according to their preferences. Users may also subscribe to the project newsletter only after providing explicit opt-in consent via dedicated consent checkboxes, which require the positive action of the user (**Figure 7**).

¹² AI-PROGNOSIS website’s Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/privacy-policy>

Subscribe to our newsletter

Enter your email address

Subscribe

I have read and agree to the [Privacy Policy](#).

I agree to receive Newsletters.

Figure 7 Newsletter subscription form with GDPR-compliant consent checkboxes

In line with GDPR requirements, users are informed of their rights, including the right of access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, data portability, objection, and the right to withdraw consent at any time. Instructions on how to exercise these rights, including contact details, are provided in the Privacy Policy.

No sensitive personal data are processed through the website. Technical and organisational measures are in place to ensure data security and confidentiality, in accordance with applicable EU and national data protection legislation.

3.1.2 Social media

Social media remains a key communication tool for AI-PROGNOSIS, supporting visibility, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of project results. The project maintains an active presence across six platforms: LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and more recently, Bluesky (**Table 1**).

These channels are used to share project updates, results, event announcements, and educational content with a broad and diverse audience. During this reporting period, Bluesky was introduced in response to changes on X, helping ensure continued engagement, particularly with healthcare professionals and digital health communities.

All accounts follow the project's visual identity guidelines and are linked through the AI-PROGNOSIS website. Posting frequency remains steady, with on average two updates per week across the main platforms.

Table 1 Social media channels

Social media channel	Handle in the channel	Reference
LinkedIn	@ai-prognosis	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ai-prognosis/
X	@aiprognosis	https://twitter.com/aiprognosis
Facebook	@AI-PROGNOSIS	https://www.facebook.com/AIPROGNOSIS
Instagram	@aiprognosis	https://www.instagram.com/aiprognosis/?next=%2F
YouTube	@AI-PROGNOSIS	AI-PROGNOSIS - YouTube
Bluesky	@aiprognosis.bsky.social	https://bsky.app/profile/aiprognosis.bsky.social

To date, AI-PROGNOSIS has 1375 followers across all social media accounts, reflecting a 24% increase since M18 (

Figure 8).

Figure 8 Number of AI-PROGNOSIS social media followers

3.1.2.1 LinkedIn

As of M32, LinkedIn has remained the most active social media channel for AI-PROGNOSIS. It serves as a key platform for engaging with professional audiences and sharing updates on project milestones, events, and publications. The LinkedIn page currently has 869 followers, reflecting a 34% increase since M18 (Figure 9).

Figure 9 AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn profile and followers demographics

The majority of AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn followers come from academic, research, and technology-oriented sectors, with the top industries being Higher Education (15.9%), Research Services (11.6%), and IT Services and IT Consulting (8.6%). Additional representation from Hospitals and Health Care (6.3%), Biotechnology Research (5%), and Software Development (4.5%) highlights engagement from both clinical and technical communities, reflecting the project’s interdisciplinary scope and relevance to healthcare innovation. Geographically, most AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn followers are based in Greece, followed by audiences in Portugal, the United Kingdom, Spain, Germany, Belgium, and Cyprus. This geographic distribution reflects the consortium’s footprint and demonstrates outreach across multiple EU countries (**Figure 9**).

To maintain engagement, on average two posts are published per week. Content typically includes project updates, participation in events, awareness campaigns, highlights of project milestones and achievements, and news from consortium partners (**Figure 10**).

Figure 10 AI-PROGNOSIS presence on LinkedIn

With steady growth and consistent interaction, LinkedIn remains a main channel for maintaining professional engagement and sharing project progress with relevant stakeholders.

3.1.2.2 Instagram

The AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account was launched in M7 to support outreach through visual content and connect with broader audiences (Figure 11).

Instagram is used to share visual highlights of project activities, including posts, reels, and stories. The page focuses on sharing educational materials, updates, and interactive content related to the project. Although similar in scope to updates on other platforms, the use of visual formats supports accessibility and visibility among wider audiences.

Figure 11 AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram profile

The page currently has 272 followers. The number of followers has increased by more than 2.6 times since M18, making Instagram the fastest-growing AI-PROGNOSIS social media account during the reporting period.

Based on Instagram insights, the AI-PROGNOSIS account over November-January 2026, recorded a total of 2,321 views, reaching 288 accounts (**Figure 12**). The majority of views came from followers (61.1%), while a substantial proportion (38.9%) originated from non-followers, indicating that the content also reached audiences beyond the existing follower base.

In terms of content type, posts generated the highest engagement, accounting for 81.7% of total views, followed by stories (12.8%) and reels (5.5%). This distribution indicates that static visual posts are currently the most effective format for communicating project-related information on Instagram, while stories and reels play a complementary role.

The most viewed content included Learning Hub articles focused on PD awareness and patient education, as well as posts promoting the online survey hosted on the project website. This reflects audience's interest in educational resources and opportunities to actively engage with the project.

Account insights

Views ⓘ

2,321

Views

Followers	61.1%
Non-followers	38.9%
<hr/>	
Accounts reached	288

By content type

Top content based on views

[See all](#)

Figure 12 AI-PROGNOSIS Instagram account insights

Overall, Instagram represents the second most active AI-PROGNOSIS social media channel, complementing LinkedIn by supporting visual communication, driving traffic to website content, and increasing the visibility of patient-focused and educational materials.

3.1.2.3 X

The AI-PROGNOSIS X account has been used for real-time updates, event announcements, and visibility efforts targeting the broader research and digital health space (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13 AI-PROGNOSIS X profile

Between M18 and M20, the number of followers on X dropped sharply from 316 to 123. This decline was attributed to platform-wide changes, such as algorithm updates and the removal of inactive or spam accounts, which impacted engagement across many users and projects. A slight recovery followed, with follower numbers increasing to 135 by M32.

Despite the reduced follower count, the account has remained active and continues to be used for sharing project milestones and supporting ongoing dissemination efforts.

In addition, the AI-PROGNOSIS joined four targeted Communities on X: *Twitter Health*, *Health Tech / Digital Health* and *AI in Healthcare* (with approximately 16.9K, 4.6K and 3.6K members respectively) and the *Parkinson's Community* (159 members). These Communities provide opportunities for thematic outreach and engagement with specialised audiences interested in digital health and Parkinson's disease (Figure 14).

Figure 14 X Communities joined by AI-PROGNOSIS

Overall, X continues to serve as a relevant channel for thematic communication and outreach activities, complementing the project's broader social media presence.

3.1.2.4 Facebook

The AI-PROGNOSIS Facebook page continues to serve as a supplementary platform to reach broader and less specialised audiences, particularly the general public. The page is used to share project updates, educational content, and event highlights (Figure 15).

Figure 15 AI-PROGNOSIS Facebook profile

As of M32, the page has 26 followers, showing a small increase compared to M18 (24 followers). Engagement on Facebook remains limited, particularly when compared to other project communication channels.

In line with the approach described in D6.3, AI-PROGNOSIS explored outreach through PD-related Facebook groups. However, some previously joined groups are no longer active, and posting is restricted in several communities due to moderation policies. As a result, group-based outreach is currently limited, with posts shared primarily in active communities such as “Living With Parkinson’s Disease”, when permitted.

Facebook remains a secondary but supportive channel in the project’s overall communication strategy, particularly for informal and visual content.

3.1.2.5 Bluesky

Bluesky was introduced as a new communication channel for AI-PROGNOSIS in M20, following changes in engagement levels on X. The aim was to explore alternative platforms for reaching health professionals and maintaining digital visibility (Figure 16).

Figure 16 AI-PROGNOSIS Bluesky profile

As of M32, the AI-PROGNOSIS Bluesky account has 51 followers, compared to 6 in M20. Bluesky remains experimental in scope and reach, but it is monitored as an additional channel for targeted communication.

3.1.2.6 YouTube

The AI-PROGNOSIS YouTube channel was launched in M7 to support visual storytelling and share video content related to project activities (Figure 17). As of M32, the channel has 22 subscribers and includes 10 videos and 2 short videos, compared to 5 videos reported in the previous period (D6.3). The content covers topics such as interviews with project partners and awareness-related initiatives.

Figure 17 AI-PROGNOSIS YouTube profile

YouTube remains a complementary platform within the broader media strategy and is primarily used for hosting and sharing audiovisual materials via the website and social media channels.

3.1.3 Newsletter

The AI-PROGNOSIS newsletter¹³ continues to serve as a regular communication tool to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, events, and key highlights. Issued quarterly since M3, four newsletters were released during the current reporting period (M19–M32), bringing the total number of published newsletters to eight (**Figure 18**).

Figure 18 AI-PROGNOSIS Newsletter

Newsletter content is tailored to different audiences and presented in clear, reader-friendly language. It includes project news updates, event recaps, interviews, publications, and other relevant developments. Newsletters are distributed via Wix Email marketing, promoted on social media, and made available for download on the project website. In addition, newsletters are uploaded to the Zenodo OpenAIRE repository¹⁴ to support wider dissemination and open access. The project also continues to issue a LinkedIn newsletter¹⁵, introduced in M10.

As of M32, the LinkedIn newsletter has 468 subscribers, while 74 subscribers receive the newsletter via email marketing, resulting in a total of 542 subscribers (**Figure 19**). This represents a 29% increase in newsletter subscribers compared to the previous reporting period (D6.3).

¹³ AI-PROGNOSIS Newsletter, <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/newsletters>

¹⁴ Zenodo OpenAIRE

https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&f=shared_with_me%3Afalse&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

¹⁵ AI-PROGNOSIS LinkedIn Newsletter, <https://www.linkedin.com/newsletters/ai-prognosis-7178700112292921344/>

Figure 19 Number of AI-PROGNOSIS newsletter subscribers

Newsletters made available via Zenodo have accumulated 1,874 downloads (as of 19 February 2026), further supporting visibility through open-access dissemination channels.

Together, these efforts ensure continued visibility, transparency, and engagement with a growing community of stakeholders.

3.1.4 Major media

The project's communication strategy foresees engagement with national and EU-level media once tangible project results are available, in line with the defined KPIs (5 national and 2 EU-level media (TV/Radio) presences). Up to M32, no major media presence has been achieved. This reflects the project's approach to engaging major media outlets only when results can be clearly presented to a wider audience.

With tangible results now emerging, major media outreach is planned for the upcoming period. Initial actions include planned contact with Euronews to explore opportunities for EU-level coverage, as well as participation in the Aristotle Innovation Forum¹⁶ (May 17-23, 2026; <https://aristotleforum.auth.gr/>), where interviews and media interactions may take place. The focus of the next reporting period will be on presenting project outcomes in a clear and accessible way for national and EU-level media.

3.1.5 Contribution of partners to online visibility

Consortium partners continued to contribute to the project's online visibility through their communication activities (**Figure 20**).

During the reporting period, partner activities took place primarily on social media, with a strong focus on LinkedIn. Content covered awareness initiatives, plenary meetings, the project survey, and general project updates, and was shared through both institutional accounts and individual professional profiles. These actions supported the project's visibility across international and regional audiences.

Partners also disseminated information about the project survey through social media posts, including multilingual posts in English, French, Spanish, and Swedish. Posts included QR

¹⁶ Aristotle Innovation forum, [Speakers – Aristotle Innovation Forum](#)

codes linking directly to the surveys and were targeted at people with Parkinson’s disease, caregivers, and healthcare professionals.

In addition, partners provided self-recorded video materials, which were used to develop project videos for awareness days and outreach activities and subsequently shared through social media and institutional channels.

Figure 20 Examples of AI-PROGNOSIS partner's online activities on social media

Detailed records of partner-led dissemination and communication activities are maintained in the project’s Dissemination and Communication tracking file, which was established at the start of the project and is regularly updated by consortium partners.

Overall, these partner-led online activities contributed to maintaining and extending the digital visibility of AI-PROGNOSIS across different stakeholder groups.

In addition to consortium-led activities, AI-PROGNOSIS was featured through external online channels in the context of World Parkinson’s Day. This included an interview-based article¹⁷ published by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) on its website, as well as a related video¹⁸ published on HaDEA’s YouTube channel. Both featured the project coordinator, and presented the project’s objectives, approach, and stakeholder-driven development of AI-based tools for PD diagnosis and care. These features supported EU-level visibility of the project beyond consortium communication channels.

3.2 Publications

3.2.1 Scientific publications

During the reporting period M19–M32, the AI-PROGNOSIS project published six scientific publications, including two peer-reviewed journal articles and four international conference

¹⁷ https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/news/world-parkinsons-day-horizon-project-ai-prognosis-using-ai-improve-parkinsons-diagnosis-and-care-2025-04-11_en

¹⁸ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NVANq_P48Ps

papers. These publications address key project themes such as AI-based prediction of PD progression, trustworthy and co-created AI systems, and stakeholder-centred perspectives in digital health.

The following publications were produced between M19–M32:

1. Chatzis, C., et al. (2025). A Deep Learning Approach for Parkinsonian Tremor Assessment Using Wearables. IEEE HealthCom 2025¹⁹.
2. Moustaklis, D., et al. (2025). On capturing effects of medication change in Parkinson's disease with wrist accelerometry-based digital biomarkers. IEEE HealthCom 2025²⁰.
3. Rizou, V., et al (2025, November). PDualNet: A Deep Learning Framework for Joint Prediction of Parkinson's Disease Progression Subtype and MDS-UPDRS Scores. Scientific Reports²¹.
4. Gerasimou, I., et al. (2025, December). Wrist Accelerometry-based Digital Assessment of Slowness of Movement in Parkinson's Disease: a Multi-Cohort Analysis. Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC 2025), July 14–17, 2025²².
5. Alves, B., et al (2025, August). Stakeholder Perspectives on Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence for Parkinson's Disease Management Using a Co-creation Approach: A Qualitative Study. Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR)²³.
6. Luckhaus, J., et al (2025, January). Co-designing a “win-win” in predictive AI: First results from interviews and focus groups with persons with Parkinson's Disease. Medical Informatics Europe 2025 Conference²⁴.

Table 2 presents key impact metrics for the project's publications in scientific journals/conferences and published, scientific deliverables so far. All scientific publications produced during the M19–M32 reporting period were made openly available via the Zenodo²⁵ repository, supporting open access and increasing the discoverability of project results. As of 23 February 2026, scientific publications and deliverables have collectively recorded over 1,000 and 1,200 downloads, respectively, indicating interest from the scientific and clinical communities. Citation counts, retrieved via Google Scholar²⁶, remain modest, which is expected given the recent publication dates and the typical citation time lag.

As of M32, AI-PROGNOSIS has produced a total of ten scientific publications, including four reported in D6.3, of which four have been published in peer-reviewed journals. These efforts contribute toward the project's target of 20 peer-reviewed publications.

Table 2 Impact metrics of scientific publications and deliverables; n/a: not applicable; impact factors retrieved from the official webpage of the journals.

Publication	Journal Impact Factor	Citations (Google scholar)	Downloads (Zenodo)
Publications in Scientific Journals / Conferences			

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/18469204>

²⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/18491523>

²¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-25812-9>

²² Wrist Accelerometry-based Digital Assessment of Slowness of Movement in Parkinson's Disease: a Multi-Cohort Analysis | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore

²³ <https://www.jmir.org/2025/1/e73710>

²⁴ <https://ebooks.iospress.nl/doi/10.3233/SHTI250325>

²⁵ https://zenodo.org/me/uploads?q=&f=shared_with_me%3Afalse&l=list&p=1&s=10

²⁶ <https://scholar.google.com/>

Publication	Journal Impact Factor	Citations (Google scholar)	Downloads (Zenodo)
Ziogas, I., et al. (2023). Bispectral analysis of Parkinsonian rest tremor: New characterization and classification insights pre-/post-DBS and medication treatment. <i>IEEE Access</i> , 11, 114459-114474.	3.6	14	108
Alves, B., et al. (2024). MoveONParkinson: developing a personalized motivational solution for Parkinson's disease management. <i>Frontiers in Public Health</i> , 12, 1420171.	3.4	4	59
Rizou, V., et al. (2025). PDualNet: a deep learning framework for joint prediction of Parkinson's disease progression subtype and MDS-UPDRS scores. <i>Scientific Reports</i> , 15(1), 41931.	3.9	1	228
Alves, B., et al. (2025). Stakeholder Perspectives on Trustworthy AI for Parkinson Disease Management Using a Co-creation Approach: Qualitative Exploratory Study. <i>Journal of Medical Internet Research</i> , 27, e73710.	6.0	1	166
Chatzis, T., et al. (2025, October). A Deep Learning Approach for Parkinsonian Tremor Assessment Using Wearables. In <i>2025 IEEE International Conference on E-health Networking, Application & Services (HealthCom)</i> (pp. 1-6). IEEE.	n/a	-	14
Alves, B., et al. (2024, November). An agile co-creation approach for designing a comprehensive digital motor assessment test for Parkinson's Disease patients. In <i>Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Software Development and Technologies for Enhancing Accessibility and Fighting Info-exclusion</i> (pp. 377-383).	n/a	-	151
Stergioulas, A., et al. (2024, June). Assessing motor skills in Parkinson's Disease using smartphone-based video analysis and machine learning. In <i>Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments</i> (pp. 562-568).	n/a	2	213
Moustaklis, A., et al. (2025, October). On capturing effects of medication change in Parkinson's disease with wrist accelerometry-based digital biomarkers. In <i>2025 IEEE International Conference on E-health Networking, Application & Services (Healthcom)</i> (pp. 1-5). IEEE.	n/a	-	7
Gerasimou, I., et al. (2025, July). Wrist accelerometry-based digital assessment of slowness of movement in Parkinson's disease: A multi-cohort analysis. In <i>2025 47th Annual International Conference of the IEEE</i>	n/a	1	38

Publication	Journal Impact Factor	Citations (Google scholar)	Downloads (Zenodo)
Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.			
Luckhaus, J., et al. (2025). Co-Designing a "win-win" in Predictive AI: First Results from Interviews and Focus Groups with Persons with Parkinson's Disease. <i>Studies in Health Technology and Informatics</i> , 327, 263-267.	n/a	-	131
Published scientific deliverables			
D2.1 / Initial report on user research and co-creation	-	-	138
D2.2 / Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (fundamental version)	-	-	188
D2.3 / Initial report on domain review and datasets	-	-	121
D3.1 / First report on digital biomarkers for PD	-	-	480
D3.2 / First report on predictive modelling for PD	-	-	209
D5.1 / Study initiation package (dBM-DEV study)	-	-	150

During M19–M32, one additional peer-reviewed journal publication was accepted and is awaiting publication:

1. Saad, A, et al. (2026). Clinical AI is not (yet) trustworthy-but it could be. *Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR)*

In addition, several manuscripts are currently submitted, under review, or planned for submission:

Peer-reviewed Journals:

- Dias, S. B., et al. AI-driven Cognitive and Motor Digital Assessment of Parkinson's Disease: a Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Nature Aging*. Under second review.
- Dias, S. B., et al. From risk to response: AI methods for Parkinson's disease assessment, monitoring, and medication response. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*. Submitted.
- Luckhaus, J., et al. Balancing Hope and Harm: A Qualitative Exploration of Ethical Aspects of Using AI in Parkinson's Disease. *JMIR AI*. Submitted (preprint available).

Peer-reviewed Conferences:

- Gerasimou I, et al. Assessment of Fine Motor Skills Impairment in Parkinson's Disease using Touchscreen Typing Dynamics: a Multi-Cohort Analysis. *EUSIPCO 2026*. Submitted.
- Wang F, et al. Rapid eye movement sleep behavior disorder (RBD). *EUSIPCO 2026*. Submitted.

- Charisis, V., et al. Multimodal digital phenotyping in psoriatic arthritis, Parkinson's disease, and breast cancer: Tri-project insights from iPROLEPSIS, AI-PROGNOSIS, and REBECCA. DSAI 2026. Submitted.

Planned submissions:

- Luckhaus, J., et al. Comparing Stakeholders' Experiences and Perceptions of Parkinson's Disease Management and Technologies: an International Survey. JMIR mHealth and uHealth. Planned for submission.
- Moustaklis, D., et al. Wearable-derived sleep and activity metrics identify hallmarks of Parkinson's disease. npj Digital Medicine. Planned for submission.
- Planned abstract submissions to the International Congress of Parkinson's Disease and Movement Disorders (MDS Congress 2026), related to clinical studies and results generated within the project.
- Luckhaus, J., et al. Patient Perspectives on AI-Based Monitoring and Prognosis in Parkinson's Disease: Findings from a Multinational Survey. Planned for submission to Journal of Parkinson's Disease

The publication pipeline remains active, with ongoing work to publish and share AI-PROGNOSIS research results with the scientific and clinical community in the field of Parkinson's disease and digital health.

3.2.2 Publications in business magazines

During the reporting period, AI-PROGNOSIS began expanding its visibility beyond scientific audiences by targeting publications aimed at non-academic and general audiences.

In M27, the article "Smartwatches and mobile phones in the fight against Parkinson's" was published by *Thessalonikeon Polis*²⁷. The article presents ongoing research, highlighting how artificial intelligence and everyday digital devices such as smartphones and wearables can support the early detection and monitoring of PD. It introduces the concept of analysing digital behavioural data to identify early disease-related changes and discusses the role of AI as a tool to support, rather than replace, clinical decision-making.

Further outreach to business and professional media is ongoing, including a potential article in the *Health Edition of Projects Magazine*, which is currently under investigation.

3.3 Events

Events continue to be a key component of the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and communication activities. They provide opportunities to present project results, engage with stakeholders, and support collaboration across research, clinical, and industry communities. Participation in events also contributes to the project's visibility through updates on communication channels such as the website, social media, and newsletters.

During the reporting period (M19–M32), project partners actively contributed to:

- **Scientific conferences:** Participation in 5 international scientific conferences, including IEEE HealthCom 2025, EMBC 2025, DGN 2025, ISPGR 2025, and Medical Informatics Europe 2025.
- **Business and industry events:** Participation in 4 business and industry events, including the EIT Health Morning Health Talk, the NTD Shareholders Meeting, Health

²⁷ <https://thessalonikeonpolis.gr/machi-kata-tou-parkinson-tehniti-noimosini/>

Data Summit 2025, and BIAL PD Summit 2025, engaging stakeholders from the health innovation and industry ecosystem.

- **Workshops, seminars, and special sessions:** Participation in 13 workshops, seminars, and special sessions, addressing academic and clinical audiences as well as non-academic groups such as patients and healthcare professionals outside academia.
- **Demo sessions to stakeholders:** 4 hands-on demo sessions were conducted, including sessions with members of the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel using pre-MVP versions of the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications, and one demo session with clinicians for mAI-Insights. In addition, eleven co-creation workshops were carried out, supporting user feedback and iterative refinement of digital health tools.

Detailed descriptions of the events are presented in the following subsections **3.3.1** and **3.3.4**.

3.3.1 Scientific conferences

During the reporting period, AI-PROGNOSIS has participated in five scientific conferences:

1. DGN 2025, 12–15 November 2025, Berlin, Germany
2. IEEE HealthCom 2025, 21–23 October 2025, Abu Dhabi, UAE
3. EMBC 2025, 14–17 July 2025, Copenhagen, Denmark
4. ISPGR 2025 30 June – 3 July 2025, Maastricht, Netherlands
5. Medical Informatics Europe 2025 Conference, 19–21 May 2025, Glasgow, Scotland

The AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented at the DGN 2025 – German Society of Neurology Congress (**Figure 21**), an annual event bringing together clinicians and experts in neurology (12–15 November 2025, Berlin, Germany). NTD delivered a presentation introducing the AI-PROGNOSIS project and its relevance for clinical practice.

Figure 21 DGN 2025 – German Society of Neurology Congress

AI-PROGNOSIS also participated in the IEEE HealthCom 2025 Conference, held 21–23 October 2025 and hosted by Khalifa University in Abu Dhabi, UAE (**Figure 22**). The event brought together experts in digital health, artificial intelligence, and biomedical technologies to explore innovative solutions for non-communicable diseases. The project teams from AUTH and CERTH contributed through scientific presentations, an award-winning paper, a panel discussion on digital health collaboration, and the co-organisation of a thematic workshop.

Figure 22 IEEE HealthCom 2025

At the 47th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC 2025), held in Copenhagen, Denmark, from 14–17 July, 2025, AUTH presented the paper “*Wrist Accelerometry-based Digital Assessment of Slowness of Movement in Parkinson’s Disease: a Multi-Cohort Analysis*” (**Figure 23**). This study focused on developing a digital biomarker (dBM) for assessing upper limb slowness of movement in PD using wrist accelerometer data passively captured during daily living.

Figure 23 EMBC 2025

The AI-PROGNOSIS project was also presented at the 2025 International Symposium of Gait and Posture Research (ISPGR), held in Maastricht, Netherlands from June 30 to July 3, 2025 (Figure 24). AUTH presented the project during the scientific session titled “Measures, measures, measures... and what about the outcomes?”.

Figure 24 ISPGR 2025

At the Medical Informatics Europe (MIE) 2025 Conference, held in Glasgow, Scotland, from 19–21 May 2025, UU presented the paper “Co-Designing a ‘Win-Win’ in Predictive AI: First

Results from Interviews and Focus Groups with Persons with Parkinson’s Disease” (Figure 25). The study, part of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, explored the perspectives of people with Parkinson’s disease (PwP) involved in the co-design of AI tools for PD care. The aim was to understand PwP perspectives on AI tools and identify factors influencing their engagement.

Figure 25 MIE 2025

As of M32, the AI-PROGNOSIS project has participated in a total of fifteen scientific conferences – ten reported in D6.3 and five during the current reporting period. This reflects the project’s continuous engagement with the scientific and clinical research communities and its commitment to high-impact dissemination in the fields of PD, artificial intelligence, and digital health.

Looking ahead, AI-PROGNOSIS is exploring participation in major scientific and professional events in 2026. In particular, involvement in the International Congress of Parkinson’s Disease and Movement Disorders (MDS 2026, Seoul, October 2026) is under consideration, including possible abstract submissions.

Further opportunities being assessed include the German Congress for Parkinson’s and Movement Disorders (April 2026), Innovation Forum (May 2026), IEEE 12th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT) 2026, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates (26 - 29 October 2026), IEEE-EMBS International Conference on Body Sensor Networks (BSN) (October 2026, Porto, Portugal), the Congress of the European Academy of Neurology (June 2026), and other European neurology and innovation-focused events. These activities aim to support dissemination of project results and engagement with clinical, research, and other related communities.

3.3.2 Business and industry events

Engagement with business and industry stakeholders is an important part of the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination strategy, supporting awareness, exchange, and dialogue around the project’s results and approaches. During M19–M32, the project participated in four business and industry events:

Following the DGN 2025 – German Society of Neurology Congress (12–15 November 2025, Berlin, Germany), the AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented at an NTD Shareholders Meeting attended by approximately 20 participants. The shareholders are primarily neurologists and psychiatrists. The meeting provided an opportunity to share project updates and encourage dissemination of AI-PROGNOSIS within clinical practices and professional networks (**Figure 26**).

Figure 26 NTD Shareholders Meeting

In June 2025, the AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented at the 1st Morning Health Talk – Greece, part of the EIT Health Morning Health Talks series. The event, titled “Co-Creating Health Innovation Ecosystems: Empowering Providers and Citizens Beyond Financial Incentives”, was organised by EIT Health Greece in Athens. AUTH delivered an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project (**Figure 27**). The session brought together stakeholders from across the health innovation ecosystem, including representatives from EIT Health, European Digital Innovation Hubs, Living Labs, public authorities, hospitals, digital health consultants, private health insurance providers, homecare services, and telemedicine companies.

Figure 27 EIT Health Morning Health Talk

At Health Data Summit 2025, held on March 18–19 2025 in Brussels and organised by the European Institute for Innovation Through Health Data (i~HD), AUTH presented the AI-PROGNOSIS project and chaired the session: “Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice” **Figure 28**. The event brought together policymakers, industry

representatives, healthcare organisations, and research initiatives, supporting discussion on the practical implementation of trustworthy AI in digital health.

Figure 28 Health Data Summit 2025

The BIAL PD Summit 2025 was held on 14–15 February 2025 in Lisbon, Portugal, focusing on recent advances in PD research and clinical care. Dr Monica Kurtis (FIN) co-chaired the summit. The AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented during a session, where AUTH highlighted how machine learning and artificial intelligence approaches developed within the project can support early detection, disease monitoring, and personalised treatment strategies in Parkinson’s disease (Figure 29).

Figure 29 BIAL PD Summit 2025

Overall, AI-PROGNOSIS engaged in ten business and industry events across the project duration, six of which were already reported in D6.3 and four in this report.

3.3.3 Workshops, seminars, and special sessions

During M19–M32, the project was presented in thirteen workshops, seminars, and special sessions reaching academic and clinical audiences as well as non-academic groups such as patients, healthcare professionals outside academia, and innovation stakeholders:

1. AI-PROGNOSIS project presentation to MSc students, FMH, January 2026
2. Non-academic outreach session with people living with PD, TUD, January 2026
3. Lecture: “Wearables and Video Analysis for Parkinson’s Disease and other Movement Disorders”, MDS course “Advances in Technology and Artificial Intelligence Applications in Movement Disorders”, FIN, December 2025

4. Webinar: “Parkinson’s Disease and Artificial Intelligence”, organised by UU, November 2025
5. Presentation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project within the “Neuroscience and Neurodegeneration” MSc programme, AUTH, Thessaloniki, Greece, November 2025
6. Lecture to PhD students, seminar “Métodos de Investigação Avançada em Motricidade Humana”, FMH, Portugal, November 2025
7. Panel session: “Digital Bridges for Better Health: AI Innovation from Europe to the Middle East and North Africa (MENA)” at IEEE HealthCom 2025 (AUTH, CERTH), October 2025
8. Workshop: “AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact” at IEEE HealthCom 2025 (AUTH, CERTH), October 2025
9. Parkinson Patient Day 2025, organised by TUD, Dresden, Germany, April 2025
10. PANOS Network Meeting 2025 – Sponsors & Therapists, organised by TUD, Dresden, Germany, April 2025
11. Special session: “Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice” as part of Health Data Summit, Brussels, Belgium, AUTH, March 2025
12. Seminar presentation: “Ethics in hybrid intelligent healthcare and care – emerging issues and approaches in dealing with Parkinson’s Disease”, OxSTAI network, University of Oxford, March 2025
13. Project presentation to MSc students of Advanced Practice in Neurological Physiotherapy, Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal, FMH, January 2025

In January 2026, the AI-PROGNOSIS project was presented to MSc students of Advanced Practice in Neurological Physiotherapy at the Health School of the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal. The presentation was delivered by FMH-ULisboa and took place within the curricular unit “Technology Allied to Neurological Physiotherapy”. It introduced the overall objectives, scope, and approach of the AI-PROGNOSIS project and supported dissemination of the project’s web survey. The session was attended by eight MSc students (**Figure 30**).

Figure 30 AI-PROGNOSIS presentation at MSc students

In January 2026, a non-academic outreach session with people with Parkinson’s disease (PwP) was organised by TUD in an online format. The session involved eight people with PD and focused on collecting qualitative feedback related to the mAI-Care app and its expected use in daily life. During the session, information about the project was presented, followed by questions aimed at clarifying specific user needs and requirements for the mAI-Care application, as well as open questions related to its perceived usefulness and potential barriers to use. The discussion provided valuable patient perspectives supporting the ongoing user-centred development and co-creation of project activities.

In December 2025, AI-PROGNOSIS was presented during the MDS course “Advances in Technology and Artificial Intelligence Applications in Movement Disorders”. The lecture “Wearables and Video Analysis for Parkinson’s Disease and other Movement Disorders” introduced the project, its clinical study and highlighted how wearable sensors, video analysis, and AI can support digital assessment and monitoring of Parkinson’s disease (**Figure 31**).

The session reached an international audience, with 60 participants on site and 115 online, including neurologists, clinical fellows, researchers, and industry representatives.

Figure 31 AI-PROGNOSIS presentation at MDS course

In November 2025, UU organised the webinar in Swedish titled “*PD and AI – What does AI mean for those of us living with PD*”. The webinar focused on living with PD and how AI can help and provided a short overview of the project as an example of how AI in PD can be realised. To gain a better understanding of the needs of people with Parkinson’s disease (PwP), participants were invited to submit specific questions in advance of the webinar. In addition, a poll was conducted at the end of the session to capture their beliefs regarding AI for PD. Most participants (69%) were positive about AI for PD, while 15% considered it promising but not yet applicable to their condition, and 13% were unsure.

A total of 125 PwP registered for the webinar, with 55 attending live. All registrants received the recording and presentation materials and had the opportunity to ask questions. The discussion highlighted PwP interest in AI-enabled prediction of disease progression, AI providing alternative ways to communicate, AI-based speech-to-text translation, prevention, AI-supported memory training or reminders, and the use of AI to compile large registries to gain deeper insights into the disease and support precision medicine. The webinar supported the collection of patient perspectives that contribute to the ongoing co-creation of educational materials and user-centred project activities.

Also in November 2025, AI-PROGNOSIS was presented as part of the lecture “The contribution of new technologies in the diagnosis and treatment of Parkinsonian syndromes”, delivered within the interdisciplinary MSc programme “Neuroscience and Neurodegeneration” at AUTH. The presentation provided an overview of the AI-PROGNOSIS project in the context of new technologies for Parkinsonian syndromes. The session was attended by approximately 40 MSc students.

In October 2025, AI-PROGNOSIS participated in the IEEE HealthCom 2025 Conference, in Abu Dhabi, UAE (Figure 32). The project contributed to the panel “Digital Bridges for Better Health: AI Innovation from Europe to the Middle East and North Africa (MENA)”. The discussion focused on challenges related to the integration of AI tools into healthcare systems,

collaboration between stakeholders, patient engagement, socio-cultural aspects of adoption, and regulatory considerations across regions. AI-PROGNOSIS was presented as a case study of AI-enabled digital health tools supporting Parkinson’s disease screening and care. Approximately 20–30 participants attended the panel session.

AI-PROGNOSIS also contributed to the workshop “AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact”, organised jointly with the iPROLEPSIS Horizon Europe project. The workshop included research contributions on Parkinson’s disease, psoriatic arthritis, multiple sclerosis, and post-stroke rehabilitation. Two presentations were based on AI-PROGNOSIS research:

- Chatzis et al., A Deep Learning Approach for Parkinsonian Tremor Assessment Using Wearables
- Moustaklis et al., On capturing effects of medication change in Parkinson’s disease with wrist accelerometry-based digital biomarkers.

The paper by Chatzis et al. received the Best Workshop Paper Award, highlighting the scientific quality of the AI-PROGNOSIS contribution.

Figure 32 IEEE HealthCom panel and workshop

To mark World Parkinson’s Day in April 2025, project partner TUD presented AI-PROGNOSIS at two events in Dresden (Figure 33):

- Parkinson Patient Day 2025 (11 April), a public event aimed at informing and empowering people living with Parkinson’s disease, and
- PANOS Network Meeting 2025 – Sponsors & Therapists (12 April), a professional gathering focused on collaboration and innovation in Parkinson’s care.

Both events supported direct engagement with patients and healthcare professionals and increased awareness of the project’s objectives.

Figure 33 TUD events

In March 2025, AI-PROGNOSIS was presented at Health Data Summit 2025 (**Figure 28**). The project contributed to the session “Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice”, which focused on how European research initiatives are applying principles of trustworthy AI in real-world digital health contexts. During the session, AI-PROGNOSIS presented its approach to developing trustworthy AI tools for Parkinson’s disease screening and care and introduced an early preview of the Parkinson’s disease risk assessment tool currently under co-design. The session attracted more than 50 participants and generated active discussion, reflecting the growing interest and support for integrating trustworthy AI into healthcare.

Also in March 2025, AI-PROGNOSIS was presented at a seminar hosted by Oxford Network for Sustainable and Trustworthy AI in Health and Care (OxSTAI)²⁸. The presentation, titled “Ethics in hybrid intelligent healthcare and care – emerging issues and approaches in dealing with Parkinson’s Disease”, used the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem as a tangible case study to illustrate how AI can be implemented in healthcare and care settings, and how principles of Trustworthy AI can be applied and extended in practice. The seminar discussed ethical and regulatory considerations related to AI-enabled healthcare systems, including challenges around responsibility, accountability, and implementation within complex digital ecosystems. The session was attended by computer and AI scientists, medical professionals and researchers, ethicists, and psychiatric health consultants, supporting interdisciplinary discussion on responsible and trustworthy AI deployment in clinical contexts.

In January 2025, FMH presented the project to MSc students of Advanced Practice in Neurological Physiotherapy at the Health School of the Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal, Portugal (**Figure 34**). The presentation introduced the project and shared progress on motor and cognitive assessment tools, while also supporting dissemination of the project’s web survey.

Figure 34 AI-PROGNOSIS presentation to MSc students of Advanced Practice in Neurological Physiotherapy

To date, eighteen workshops, seminars, and special sessions have been delivered – five reported in D6.3 and thirteen during the current period – demonstrating sustained multi-stakeholder engagement and outreach.

The project will further contribute to scientific exchange through an accepted special session at EUSIPCO 2026, entitled “Digital Biomarkers for Chronic Diseases”.

²⁸ Oxford Network for Sustainable and Trustworthy AI in Health and Care (OxSTAI) — Ethox Centre

3.3.4 Demo sessions to stakeholders

Demo sessions are part of the AI-PROGNOSIS dissemination and stakeholder engagement strategy and are planned to support hands-on interaction with the project's digital tools once suitable versions become available.

During the M19–M32 reporting period, demo activities focused on early, pre-MVP versions of the applications and were conducted with members of the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel and with clinicians. Specifically:

- One hands-on demo session for mAI-Health involving PwP (29 April 2025).
- Two hands-on demo sessions for mAI-Care involving PwP (10 and 13 June 2025), and
- One demo session with clinicians for mAI-Insights (30 September 2025)

These sessions followed the hands-on experience and feedback workshop format described in section 5.3.5 of Deliverable D2.5. They provided participants with an overview of the applications and focused on collecting feedback on usability, clarity, and understanding of the tools.

In addition to these demo-style sessions, co-creation activities were carried out during the project to support user research and application design. These activities included:

- Two AI Design & Specification workshops with PwP, focusing on trustworthy AI, user needs, and expectations for the mAI-Health and mAI-Care tools
- Two AI Design & Specification workshops with healthcare professionals (HCPs), addressing clinical relevance, data use, and integration into care pathways
- Four UI/UX design workshops with PwP, conducted in two rounds, focusing on interface design, data visualisations, and usability of the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications, and
- Three UI/UX design workshops with HCPs, focusing on dashboards, reports, and presentation of AI outputs in the mAI-Insights application.

These co-creation workshops involved PwP and HCP participants from multiple countries and contributed directly to the iterative refinement of the AI-PROGNOSIS applications. Detailed descriptions of the workshop formats, participant profiles, and findings are provided in Deliverable D2.5, Section 5.3.

Further hands-on experience and feedback sessions are planned for May 2026, during which potential end-users will be invited to use the three AI-PROGNOSIS applications over a defined period and provide structured feedback.

4 Educational material

4.1.1 Educational content development strategy

The educational content development strategy for AI-PROGNOSIS is to create engaging educational content to raise PD awareness through different stakeholders. Tailored articles, quizzes, videos, and dictionary entries provide disease insights, the role of AI in PD, and actionable factors that positively impact the quality of life.

To fulfil the objectives, a foundation to ensure relevant and high standard content has been developed. This foundation consists of three checklists for general educational content,

articles, and multimedia. The general checklist reflects the most basic evaluation criteria. It focuses on whether the content is engaging, raises awareness about PD, improves health literacy, and is tailored for individuals with the disease, those without it, or both. The article checklist evaluates accessibility, clarity, informativeness, and the appropriateness of the message and tone. The multimedia checklist assesses interactivity, visual appeal, simplification of complex information, and message suitability.

These checklists are assessed by different stakeholder groups (HCPs, PwP, technical partners), depending on the educational content. Educational content undergoes two rounds of review, incorporating feedback from at least two stakeholder groups. People with PD validate relevance and usability, healthcare professionals provide clinical expertise, and technical experts contribute insights on AI-PROGNOSIS tools. This structured approach ensures that all materials meet high standards of accuracy, accessibility, and impact before being shared publicly.

To further visualise the strategy, see **Table 3**, mapping activities to content topics.

Table 3 Development strategy for educational content

Content	Prodromal risk and markers in PD	Benefits of early diagnosis	How patients live with PD	AI in PD	Motor symptoms	Non-motor symptoms
Dictionary entry	X	X		X	X	X*
Article	X		X	X	X	
Infographics			X*		X*	X*
Quiz	X	X	X	X*	X	X*

Note: Items marked with an asterisk (*) indicate content that is currently under development.

To maximise knowledge and support the adoption of tools related to PD risk, progression, and medication response, UU organised a non-academic outreach webinar in November 2025 titled “Parkinson’s Disease and Artificial Intelligence – What Does AI Mean for Those of Us Living with PD”. The webinar focused on living with PD and how AI can help. The feedback from the PwP and the presentation materials from the webinar provided input for the refinement and development of further educational materials, including infographics. A more detailed description of the webinar is provided in Section 3.3.3.

All educational content is co-created and reviewed by PwP and/or HCPs, and further efforts are planned to continue involving different stakeholders in the development of the project’s educational content.

4.1.2 Dictionary entries

The purpose of the dictionary entries is to provide clear explanations of terms related to PD and AI. All reviewed dictionary entries are uploaded to the webpage of the project²⁹.

So far there are motor symptoms and prodromal stage/period provided for medical-related terms. For AI-related terms, there are explanations of AI, algorithms, machine learning, predictive AI, and generative AI.

²⁹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/dictionary>

4.1.3 Articles

During the M19–M32 reporting period, the AI-PROGNOSIS project produced six new tailored articles, published on the project website, with focus on understanding PD impact in daily life and the role of AI-based digital health solutions³⁰. The first four listed articles are connected to either mAI-Health or mAI-Care applications being developed in AI-PROGNOSIS, as well as they have been translated into Spanish, German, and French.

- **Predicting Parkinson’s progression with AI: promise and pitfalls**

Every person with Parkinson’s disease (PD) experiences a unique journey – some people’s symptoms progress slowly over many years, while others may develop severe disabilities within a shorter time.

- **Using AI to strengthen Parkinson’s diagnosis**

Diagnosing Parkinson’s disease (PD) can be challenging, especially in the early stages. The early symptoms can be subtle or overlap with other disorders, and PD is defined clinically, so there is no lab test for diagnosing PD.

- **Living with Parkinson’s Disease**

Parkinson’s disease (PD) is one of the most common neurological disorders, affecting around 10 million worldwide. It is a chronic, progressive disease. With advances in treatment, people with PD today often live long and active lives despite their diagnosis.

- **Journey to a Parkinson’s Diagnosis**

Getting an accurate diagnosis of Parkinson’s disease (PD) can be a long journey. PD is a progressive neurological disorder with no single definitive lab test, so doctors rely on clinical evaluation of symptoms.

- **Trust and Trustworthiness in AI Ethics**

In her paper "Trust and Trustworthiness in AI Ethics," Karoline Reinhardt discusses the growing conversation about trust in artificial intelligence, as AI becomes more common in the society around us.

- **A.I. Robustness: A Human-Centered Perspective on Technological Challenges and Opportunities**

The paper "A.I. Robustness: A Human-Centered Perspective on Technological Challenges and Opportunities," written by Andrea Tocchetti and his colleagues, looks at different challenges in ensuring the reliability and safety of artificial intelligence systems.

In addition, one article – “Sex and gender impact on Parkinson’s disease” – was developed during M1–M18 and reported in D6.3. Overall, the project has produced a total of seven educational articles to date.

4.1.4 Videos

For further educational content to raise PD awareness, one video was recorded, reviewed, and uploaded at the webpage, during the earlier project phase (M1–M18), and reported in D6.3. The video demonstrates motor symptoms from a clinical perspective and how they are

³⁰ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/articles>

vital for diagnosis. Dr Margherita Fabbri from Toulouse University Hospital provides further insights of this topic in the video³¹.

4.1.5 Quizzes

As a more interactive engagement of educational content, quizzes are developed to test the knowledge of different stakeholders. These quizzes are published on the project website and are designed to support engagement with the project’s educational materials. They aim to raise awareness of PD and provide a learning opportunity for different stakeholders³².

During the M19–M32 reporting period, three new quizzes – “AI and Early Detection of Parkinson’s”, “Living with Parkinson’s disease” and “Prodromal stage and early signs” – were developed and published on the project website. In addition, one quiz on “Basic knowledge” was developed during the earlier project phase (M1–M18) and reported in D6.3.

Overall, the project has produced a total of four educational quizzes to date.

4.1.6 Infographics

Infographics are used as an effective way of simplifying and visualising complex information, enhancing retention, and supporting engagement.

During the M19–M32 reporting period, several infographics have been under development and are planned to be completed in the near future. These include:

- “The journey to a Parkinson’s Diagnosis” – covering the pathway from phase 1, the prodromal stage (early clues), to phase 2, the motor stage (confirmation)
- “Living well”, and
- two to three infographics based on patients’ questions and information shared during the non-academic outreach sessions.

One infographic was developed during the earlier project phase (M1–M18) as part of the “Basic knowledge” quiz, which was reported in D6.3. This infographic is integrated within the quiz and is displayed to users upon completion, presenting key facts and statistics about PD in a clear and visual format (**Figure 35**).

Figure 35 “Basic knowledge” infographic

³¹ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/video>

³² <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/quizzes>

5 Clustering and networking activities

5.1.1 Collaboration with sister projects and other EU-funded initiatives

During the reporting period (M19-M32), AI-PROGNOSIS participated in several clustering and networking activities with sister projects and other EU-funded initiatives. These activities supported knowledge exchange, joint dissemination, and collaboration on shared topics related to digital health and AI for healthcare.

Key clustering activities included:

- **Workshop “AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact” (IEEE HealthCom 2025)**

AI-PROGNOSIS and iPROLEPSIS co-organised a workshop titled “AI-enabled Digital Health Tools for Non-Communicable Diseases: From Concepts to Impact” at the IEEE HealthCom 2025 conference (21–23 October 2025, Abu Dhabi, UAE). The workshop included research contributions on Parkinson’s disease, psoriatic arthritis, multiple sclerosis, and post-stroke rehabilitation. Discussion addressed AI-driven approaches for early detection, personalised treatment, and remote care in NCDs, with a focus on digital biomarkers as well as ethical and regulatory considerations.

- **Panel “Digital Bridges for Better Health: AI Innovation from Europe to the Middle East and North Africa (MENA)” (IEEE HealthCom 2025)**

AI-PROGNOSIS and iPROLEPSIS also took part in the panel discussion “Digital Bridges for Better Health: AI Innovation from Europe to the Middle East and North Africa (MENA)” at IEEE HealthCom 2025. The discussion focused on technical challenges related to integrating AI into existing healthcare IT systems, collaboration among stakeholders to ensure usability and clinical relevance, the role of patient engagement and digital literacy, socio-cultural factors affecting adoption in Europe and the MENA region, and regulatory challenges and opportunities for harmonisation.

- **Session “Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice” (Health Data Summit 2025)**

At the Health Data Summit 2025 (18–19 March 2025, Brussels), AI-PROGNOSIS was presented within the session “Trustworthy AI in Digital Health: From Guidelines to Practice”. The session focused on how European research projects apply principles of trustworthy AI in real-world digital health contexts and included presentations from other Horizon Europe projects such as iPROLEPSIS³³, TRUSTroke³⁴, and STRATIFYHF³⁵. The session addressed ethical, regulatory, and practical challenges related to the integration of AI tools into clinical environments.

- **Participation in iPROLEPSIS Meetings:**
 - 6th Plenary Meeting, 13–14 May 2025, Oxford, UK
 - 7th Plenary Meeting, 9–10 December 2025, Lisbon, Portugal

These meetings strengthened collaboration between the two projects, particularly in the area of AI-driven digital health solutions.

³³ <https://www.iprolepsis.eu/>

³⁴ <https://trustroke.eu/>

³⁵ <https://stratifyhf.eu/>

- **Stay Healthy Cluster: Communication and Dissemination Task Force online meetings**

AI-PROGNOSIS continued its involvement with sister projects in the Stay Healthy Cluster Communication and Dissemination Task Force, established in M15. During the reporting period three online meetings were held (October, July and March 2025), focusing on joint clustering and dissemination activities, and identification of shared themes across projects.

As part of this collaboration, a joint white paper titled “Trustworthy AI for Transformative Healthcare” is under discussion and development, involving AI-PROGNOSIS, SmartChange, TRUSTroke, and UMBRELLA. Three dedicated online meetings were organised to discuss the scope and content.

The white paper aims to explore shared challenges and opportunities in the use of artificial intelligence in healthcare. It addresses common topics across the participating projects, including predictive risk modelling, trustworthy AI, data privacy and ethics, and conditions for real-world uptake. It also considers market opportunities, barriers to adoption, and pathways for deployment and scalability, with the goal of identifying overlaps and sharing best practices for responsible AI use in healthcare.

Overall, this joint activity supports exchange of experience between projects, discussion of regulatory and exploitation challenges, and assessment of the current maturity of AI-based healthcare solutions. A preliminary target for completion of the white paper is April–May 2026.

5.1.2 Booster service delivery

AI-PROGNOSIS continued its engagement with the Booster initiative, following its initial application for Horizon Results Booster (HRB)³⁶ services in M11.

More specifically, within the scope of **Service 3.2: Portfolio Analysis (POA)**, between December 2024 and June 2025, the project participated in a total of four meetings with Booster experts:

- 5 December 2024 – Entry-Level Consultation Call #1: Introduction to Booster services, identification of key exploitable results (KERs), and review of the dissemination and exploitation ecosystem
- 8 January 2025 – Entry-Level Consultation Call #2: Completion of the Readiness Assessment and development of a tailored Service Roadmap for the next phases
- 27 March 2025 – Portfolio Analysis Introductory Call: Alignment on clustering objectives, including the shared use of real-world data and AI in healthcare; a stakeholder mapping exercise identified key groups such as policymakers, healthcare providers, research institutions, and digital health SMEs as common engagement targets
- 5 June 2025 – Convergence Call: Review of the clustering calendar, agreement on joint KERs, and planning of upcoming dissemination actions.

The POA aimed to support the creation of a portfolio of results collected from like-minded sister projects suitable for joint dissemination and exploitation activities. This approach supports the sustainability of project outcomes through networking, clustering, and knowledge exchange.

³⁶ Horizon Result Booster, <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

As a result, a cluster from three EU-funded projects, AI-PROGNOSIS, iPROLEPSIS³⁷ and REBECCA³⁸, was established. The current activities focused on joint dissemination of a thematic cluster centred on AI-driven digital health solutions and real-world evidence for personalized care – specifically AI-enabled tools addressing chronic conditions such as psoriatic arthritis, Parkinson’s disease, and breast cancer survivorship.

As a result of these sessions, the following key actions and deliverables were achieved:

- **Joint KER identification:**
 - Real world data collection and analysis platforms
 - AI-based digital health decision support & monitoring tools
- **Creation of shared communication materials**, including:
 - A joint news release
 - A shared PowerPoint presentation template
 - A cluster identity text for use across project websites
 - Social media templates via Canva
 - A clustering calendar with proposed event and content planning
- **Proposed joint dissemination opportunities at:**
 - Future of Health Europe 2025 (30 September – 1 October 2025, London, UK)
 - AI Health Summit – Economist Impact (26–27 November 2025, London, UK)

These recommendations were included in the Final Report provided by the Booster experts. Follow-up cluster meetings were held to discuss possible joint participation in events. As part of the Booster-supported clustering activities, preparation of a joint scientific paper for submission to DSAI 2026³⁹ is currently ongoing. The paper, titled “*Multimodal digital phenotyping in psoriatic arthritis, Parkinson’s disease, and breast cancer: Tri-project insights from iPROLEPSIS, AI-PROGNOSIS, and REBECCA*”, synthesises insights from the three Horizon Europe initiatives on multimodal digital phenotyping across different disease contexts.

To support cluster visibility, a dedicated article⁴⁰ was published on the AI-PROGNOSIS website outlining the background, shared goals, and future plans of collaboration with iPROLEPSIS and REBECCA. In parallel, a coordinated social media campaign was carried out, during which all three projects shared dedicated posts across their platforms to introduce and promote the cluster (**Figure 36**).

³⁷ iPROLEPSIS, <https://www.iprolepsis.eu/>

³⁸ REBECCA, <https://rebeccaproject.eu/>

³⁹ <https://dsai.ws/2026/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ai-prognosis.eu/news/iprolepsis%2C-ai-prognosis-%26-rebecca%3A-a-thematic-cluster-on-ai-driven-digital-health>

Figure 36 Social media campaign introducing the cluster

Following the completion of Service 3.2, Booster Service 3.5 (Audiovisual Support) was initiated in September 2025. This service aims to strengthen joint visibility of AI-driven digital health innovations and support event-based dissemination through shared audiovisual material. By the time of preparation of this deliverable, the script and draft storyboard had been provided by the Booster experts. Development of the joint video is planned as the final step, with further details to be reported in Deliverable D6.6.

5.1.3 Networking activities of partners

During the reporting period, AI-PROGNOSIS partners engaged in a range of networking activities with researchers, clinicians and industry representatives to increase awareness, share knowledge and create collaboration opportunities.

Key initiatives included:

- **Networking through the EBRAINS network**

UOXF participated in ongoing networking activities through the EBRAINS⁴¹ network. EBRAINS is a digital pan-European research infrastructure that provides digital tools and services which can be used to address challenges in brain research and brain-inspired technology development. The Ethics and Society Committee (EESC)⁴² meets monthly to review, discuss, and address arising ethical and social concerns in all activities of EBRAINS, and in the general landscape of neuroscience and neurotechnology. Participation in these discussions supported exchange on ethical and societal aspects relevant to AI-based approaches in neurological research and healthcare, including those addressed in AI-PROGNOSIS.

- **ECTRIMS 2025**

AI-PROGNOSIS partner NTD attended the 41st Congress of the European Committee for Treatment and Research in Multiple Sclerosis (ECTRIMS 2025), held on 8–10 October 2025 in Barcelona, Spain. The congress provided an opportunity to network with the international

⁴¹ EBRAINS RI - Europe's Digital Infrastructure for Brain Research

⁴² Ethics & Society | EBRAINS

neurology community and to raise visibility for AI-PROGNOSIS in the broader fields of neurodegeneration and digital health.

- **AD/PD 2025**

AI-PROGNOSIS was introduced during informal discussions with participants at the AD/PD 2025 International Conference on Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s Diseases and related neurological disorders, held from 1–5 April 2025 in Vienna, Austria.

- **AAN 2025 Annual Meeting**

AI-PROGNOSIS partner NTD attended the American Academy of Neurology (AAN) 2025 Annual Meeting (5–9 April 2025, San Diego, USA), where networking and informal exchanges supported engagement with international professionals and dissemination of the project’s goals and progress in Parkinson’s disease research.

- **Dreiländertagung 2025**

AI-PROGNOSIS partner NTD attended the Dreiländertagung 2025, the joint annual meeting of the German and Austrian Societies for Epileptology and the Swiss Epilepsy League, held on 26–29 March 2025 in Salzburg, Austria. Although the conference focused primarily on epilepsy, it brought together neurologists from multiple specialties, providing opportunities to present the AI-PROGNOSIS project and discuss its approach to AI and digital biomarkers in neurological care.

Overall, these clustering and networking activities supported collaboration with different stakeholders and strengthened the visibility of AI-PROGNOSIS in European and international research and clinical communities.

6 Dissemination and communication performance (KPIs)

This section provides an overview of the dissemination and communication performance for the period M1-M32. It builds on the baseline established in D6.3 (covering M1–M18) and includes progress achieved during the current reporting period (M19–M32). The results reflect the project’s continued efforts to increase visibility, engage key stakeholder groups, and disseminate results through a broad range of channels. An overview of target and achieved KPIs is provided in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Target and reached KPIs for M1-M32

D&C actions	What	When	Target KPI	Reached KPI M1-M18	Reached KPIs (M19-M32)	Cumulative KPIs (M1-M32)
Publications	Peer-reviewed journals	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	20 publications	4 scientific publications (2 of them in peer-reviewed journals)	6 scientific publications (2 of them in peer-reviewed journals) + 1 accepted	10 (4 of them in peer-reviewed journals)

D&C actions	What	When	Target KPI	Reached KPI M1-M18	Reached KPIs (M19-M32)	Cumulative KPIs (M1-M32)
	Business Magazines		4 publications	0	1	1
Event participation	Scientific conference presentations/posters	From M12, when initial scientific results are available	20 presentations/posters	10	5	15
	Business/Industry events and EXPOs stands/booths		3 events	5 + presence in 1 booth in MEDICA 2023	4	10
	Workshops/Special sessions/Seminars	From M18, when solid scientific results are available	8 events 50 expected attendees	5 / ~60 attendees	13 / ~450 attendees	18 / ~500 attendees
	Demo sessions to stakeholders	From M18, when alpha versions of tools are available	6 demo sessions	0 demo sessions; 2 co-creation workshops	4 demo sessions; 11 co-creation workshops	4 demo sessions; 13 co-creation workshops
Media presence	Newsletters	From M4 every three months	1000 subscribers	4 newsletters ; 407 subscribers	4 newsletters ; 542 subscribers	8 newsletters ; 542 subscribers
	Website/blog posts	From M3	4 posts/month 1000 visitors/month	Av. 4 posts per month; Av. 183 visitors/month	Av. 4 posts per month; Av. 335 visitors/month	Av. 4 posts per month; Av. 255 visitors/month
	Social media posts	From M1	2 posts/week 2000 followers	Av. 2 post/week 1107 followers	Av. 2 post/week 1375 followers	Av. 2 post/week 1375 followers
	Major media (TV/radio) presence	From M6, when tangible results are produced	5 presences in national media	0	0	0
2 presences in EU-level media			0	0	0	
Networking and clustering events			≥4 networking/joint initiatives	5 networking meetings/ 2 online	2 workshops and 1 panel	3 joint EU/international initiatives

D&C actions	What	When	Target KPI	Reached KPI M1-M18	Reached KPIs (M19-M32)	Cumulative KPIs (M1-M32)
				meetings with sister projects / Participation in 3 networking initiatives: DHU, Sister projects' cluster, Horizon Booster Services – Portfolio dissemination cluster)	session at international conference; 1 formal dissemination on cluster established via Booster; participation in 2 plenary meetings of the EU-funded project <i>iPROLEPS IS</i> ; 3 online meetings with sister projects; 5 additional networking activities	(workshop and panel at IEEE HealthCom 2025; workshop at Health Data Summit 2025); 13 networking activities (EBRAINS, DHU, Booster Services 3.2 & 3.5, iPROLEPS IS collaboration); 5 online meetings with sister projects (Stay Healthy Cluster)

Overall, dissemination and communication activities progressed steadily during the reporting period. By M32, participation in scientific conferences increased from 10 events reported in D6.3 to a total of 15, reflecting continued engagement with the scientific and clinical research communities. In parallel, the project was presented in 18 workshops, seminars, and special sessions, reaching academic and clinical audiences as well as non-academic groups, including PwP, HCPs outside academia, and professional audiences from industry, policy makers and healthcare innovation.

Ten scientific publications have been produced by M32, including four peer-reviewed journal articles. Additional manuscripts are currently under review or in preparation. In addition, one article was published in a business-oriented outlet. While the publication target has not yet been reached, output continues to increase as project results mature.

Online communication activities continued throughout the period. By M32, eight newsletters had been published, with subscriber numbers increasing from 407 at M18 to 542. Social media activity remained regular, with an average of two posts per week and growth in followers from 1,107 to 1,375. Website activity remained consistent, with an average of four posts per month. Average monthly visits increased compared to the previous period but remain below the target of 1,000 visits per month.

Clustering and networking activities expanded, including participation in two workshops and one panel session at international conferences, establishment of a formal cluster through Booster services, participation in plenary meetings of other EU-funded projects, and multiple

online and bilateral networking activities. Cumulatively, by M32, three joint EU or international initiatives and thirteen additional networking activities were recorded. In addition, preparation of a joint paper for submission to DSAI 2026 is ongoing within the established cluster. A joint white paper with sister projects is also under consideration.

Activities related to demo sessions focused on hands-on interactions with stakeholders using early, pre-MVP versions of the project's tools. By M32, four demo sessions and thirteen co-creation workshops were conducted in total, involving PwP and clinicians.

Overall, dissemination and communication activities showed steady progress across M1–M32. Areas such as scientific publications, media presence, and website traffic will receive further attention during the remaining project period. A complete update will be provided in Deliverable D6.6, "Final report on project visibility and educational material" (M48).

7 Conclusions

This midterm report (D6.5) summarises dissemination, communication, educational content development, and clustering and networking activities carried out within AI-PROGNOSIS during the M19–M32 reporting period. Building on the foundations established during the first reporting period (M1–M18), the project has continued to implement its dissemination and communication strategy across scientific, clinical, industry, and non-academic contexts.

Key observations from the reporting period include:

- **Dissemination and communication progress:** Project dissemination and communication remained active across multiple channels, including the project website, social media, newsletters, external EU-level online channels, and participation in scientific, industry, and other events. During M19–M32, six scientific publications were produced, including two peer-reviewed journal publications. Furthermore, one publication has been accepted in a peer-reviewed journal, and several manuscripts are currently submitted, under review, or in preparation. Cumulatively by M32, the project has produced ten scientific publications, including four peer-reviewed journal publications. Online activities focused on regular updates through the project website, social media, and newsletters, with steady growth in followers and subscribers during the reporting period. While average monthly website visits remain below the final target, newsletter subscriptions and social media followers increased steadily during the reporting period.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** Through dissemination and communication activities such as scientific conferences, industry events, workshops, and special sessions, the project engaged researchers, clinicians, industry representatives, and patient communities. During M19–M32, the project was presented at five scientific conferences, four business and industry events, and thirteen workshops, seminars, and special sessions. Cumulatively by M32, AI-PROGNOSIS has participated in fifteen scientific conferences, ten business and industry events, and eighteen workshops, seminars, and special sessions. In addition, four demo sessions were conducted using early pre-MVP versions of the project's tools, including sessions with members of the AI-PROGNOSIS Patient Panel for the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications and one demo session with clinicians for mAI-Insights. These sessions, together with eleven co-creation workshops involving PwP and HCP, supported feedback and user involvement in the design and refinement of the project's digital tools.

- **Clustering and networking:** Clustering and networking activities expanded during M19–M32 through collaboration with sister projects and other EU-funded initiatives, participation in joint workshops and panel sessions, involvement in cross-project meetings, the establishment of a formal cluster through Booster services, and partner-led networking activities. In addition, preparation of a joint paper for submission to DSAI 2026 is ongoing within the established cluster. A joint white paper with sister projects (SmartChange, TRUSTroke, and UMBRELLA) is also under discussion and development, with a preliminary target for completion in April–May 2026. These activities supported exchange of experience, collaboration, and increased visibility of AI-PROGNOSIS within European and international research and clinical communities.
- **Educational material:** Educational content development continued during the reporting period. New educational articles, dictionary entries, and quizzes were produced, and a non-academic outreach webinar with PwP contributed to the development of additional educational materials. Further enrichment of educational content, including the completion of planned infographics, will continue in the next phase of the project.
- **Performance monitoring:** Progress against KPIs shows that several targets related to events, workshops, networking, and online engagement have been met or exceeded at midterm. Other areas, including scientific publications, major media presence, and website traffic will be addressed during the remaining project period.

Overall, the activities implemented during M19–M32 demonstrate steady progress in increasing project visibility and stakeholder engagement across scientific, clinical, industry, and non-academic contexts. Compared to the first reporting period, dissemination and communication activities during M19–M32 expanded in scope and volume, with increased participation in scientific conferences, workshops, special sessions, and clustering initiatives, alongside continued online communication through the project website, newsletters, and social media.

In parallel, the project continued direct engagement with PwP through non-academic outreach sessions, webinars, demo sessions, and co-creation workshops, while engagement with HCPs took place primarily through co-creation workshops, professional meetings, and conference participation. These activities supported the collection of stakeholder perspectives relevant to the design and refinement of the project’s digital tools, and contributed to dissemination, exchange, and awareness of the project’s approaches and results.

The next phase will focus on consolidating mature scientific results, strengthening publication efforts, expanding outreach to broader audiences including major media, and completing the development of planned educational content. A complete assessment of dissemination and communication performance for the full project duration will be provided in Deliverable D6.6, “Final report on project visibility and educational material” (M48).